

OPEN SCIENCE GLOSSARY

1st part

OPENNESS

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APC = Article Processing Charge

An article processing charge (APC), also known as a publication fee, is a fee which is sometimes charged to authors to make a work available [open access](#) in either an [open access journal](#) or [hybrid journal](#). This fee is usually paid by an author's institution or research funder rather than by the author themselves. Some publishers waive the fee in cases of hardship. An article processing charge does not guarantee that the author retains copyright to the work, or that it will be made available under a [Creative Commons license](#). (see also TCP)

API =Application Programming Interface

In computer science the term API, or Application Programming Interface, indicates every set of procedures available to programmers, usually aggregated to form a set of tools specific for the implementation of a given task within a given programme. This term often refers to software libraries available within a certain programming language.

BLOCK

Operation which secures file changes until it is closed by its starter. Not all versioning systems use it because this practice secures the parallel development and this limits its use. In some cases the block concept is utilized only in particular contexts such as the commit context to guarantee the atomicity of actions.

BOAI = Budapest Open Access Initiative (2002)

URL <http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/>

An old tradition and a new technology have converged to make possible an unprecedented public good. The old tradition is the willingness of scientists and scholars to publish the fruits of their research in scholarly journals without payment, for the sake of inquiry and knowledge. The new technology is the internet. The public good they make possible is the world-wide electronic distribution of the peer-reviewed journal literature and completely free and unrestricted access to it by all scientists, scholars, teachers, students, and other curious minds. Removing access barriers to this literature will accelerate research, enrich education, share the learning of the rich with the poor and the poor with the rich, make this literature as useful as it can be, and lay the foundation for uniting humanity in a common intellectual conversation and quest for knowledge.

For various reasons, this kind of free and unrestricted online availability, which we will call **open access**, has so far been limited to small portions of the journal literature. But even in these limited collections, many different initiatives have shown that open access is economically feasible, that it gives readers extraordinary power to find and make use of relevant literature, and that it gives authors and their works [vast and measurable](#) new [visibility](#), [readership](#), and [impact](#). To secure these benefits for all, we call on all interested institutions and individuals to help open up access to the rest of this

literature and remove the barriers, especially the price barriers, that stand in the way. The more who join the effort to advance this cause, the sooner we will all enjoy the benefits of open access.

The literature that should be freely accessible online is that which scholars give to the world without expectation of payment. Primarily, this category encompasses their peer-reviewed journal articles, but it also includes any un-reviewed preprints that they might wish to put online for comment or to alert colleagues to important research findings. There are many degrees and kinds of wider and easier access to this literature. By "open access" to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself. The only constraint on reproduction and distribution, and the only role for copyright in this domain, should be to give authors control over the integrity of their work and the right to be properly acknowledged and cited.

While the peer-reviewed journal literature should be accessible online without cost to readers, it is not costless to produce. However, experiments show that the [overall costs](#) of providing open access to this literature are far lower than the costs of traditional forms of dissemination. With such an opportunity to save money and expand the scope of dissemination at the same time, there is today a strong incentive for professional associations, universities, libraries, foundations, and others to embrace open access as a means of advancing their missions. Achieving open access will require new cost recovery models and financing mechanisms, but the significantly lower overall cost of dissemination is a reason to be confident that the goal is attainable and not merely preferable or utopian.

To achieve open access to scholarly journal literature, we recommend two complementary strategies.

- I. [Self-Archiving](#): First, scholars need the [tools and assistance](#) to deposit their refereed journal articles in open electronic archives, a practice commonly called, self-archiving. When these archives conform to standards created by the [Open Archives Initiative](#), then search engines and other tools can treat the separate archives as one. Users then need not know which archives exist or where they are located in order to find and make use of their contents.
- II. [Open-access Journals](#): Second, scholars need the means to launch a new generation of journals committed to open access, and to help existing journals that elect to make the transition to open access. Because journal articles should be disseminated as widely as possible, these new journals will no longer invoke copyright to restrict access to and use of the material they publish. Instead they will use copyright and other tools to ensure permanent open access to all the articles they publish. Because price is a barrier to access, these new journals will not charge subscription or access fees, and will turn to other methods for covering their expenses. There are many alternative sources of funds for this purpose, including the foundations and governments that fund research, the universities and laboratories that employ researchers, endowments set up by discipline or institution, friends of the cause of open access, profits from the sale of add-ons to the basic texts, funds freed up by the demise or cancellation of journals charging traditional subscription or access fees, or even contributions from the researchers themselves. There is no need to

favour one of these solutions over the others for all disciplines or nations, and no need to stop looking for other, creative alternatives.

Open access to peer-reviewed journal literature is the goal. **Self-archiving (I.)** and a new generation of **open-access journals (II.)** are the ways to attain this goal. They are not only direct and effective means to this end, they are within the reach of scholars themselves, immediately, and need not wait on changes brought about by markets or legislation. While we endorse the two strategies just outlined, we also encourage experimentation with further ways to make the transition from the present methods of dissemination to open access. Flexibility, experimentation, and adaptation to local circumstances are the best ways to assure that progress in diverse settings will be rapid, secure, and long-lived.

The **Open Society Institute** (<https://www.opensocietyfoundations.org/>), the foundation network founded by philanthropist George Soros, is committed to providing initial help and funding to realize this goal. It will use its resources and influence to extend and promote institutional self-archiving, to launch new open-access journals, and to help an open-access journal system become economically self-sustaining. While the Open Society Institute's commitment and resources are substantial, this initiative is very much in need of other organizations to lend their effort and resources.

We invite governments, universities, libraries, journal editors, publishers, foundations, learned societies, professional associations, and individual scholars who share our vision to join us in the task of removing the barriers to open access and to build a future in which research and education in every part of the world are freer to flourish.

February 14, **2002** - Budapest, Hungary

Leslie Chan: *Bioline International*

Darius Cuplinskis: *Director, Information Program, Open Society Institute*

Michael Eisen: *Public Library of Science*

Fred Friend: *Director Scholarly Communication, University College London*

Yana Genova: *Next Page Foundation*

Jean-Claude Guédon: *University of Montreal*

Melissa Hagemann: *Program Officer, Information Program, Open Society Institute*

Stevan Harnad: *Professor of Cognitive Science, University of Southampton, Université du Québec à Montréal*

Rick Johnson: *Director, Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition (SPARC)*

Rima Kupryte: *Open Society Institute*

Manfredi La Manna: *Electronic Society for Social Scientists*

István Rév: *Open Society Institute, Open Society Archives*

Monika Segbert: *eIFL Project consultant*

Sidnei de Souza: *Informatics Director at CRIA, Bioline International*

Peter Suber: *Professor of Philosophy, Earlham College & The Free Online Scholarship Newsletter*

Jan Velterop: *Publisher, BioMed Central*

BFI = Bibliometric Research Indicator

The Danish BFI, or Bibliometric Research Indicator, is part of the performance-based model for the distribution of new base funding for universities in Denmark.

The main purpose of the Danish BFI is to reflect the universities' research activity using the measurement of number of publications.

The BFI rewards the research publications that are published in the most recognized journals within the scientific fields.

This means that it must cover all disciplines and their different publishing traditions.

CRIS = Current Research Information System

During the year 2015 more than 50 Italian universities migrated from “UGOV-ricerca” to “IRIS - Institutional Research Information System”, the new “CRIS - Current Research Information System”, developed by Cineca which integrates the open repository DSPACE with features and services requested by a research management system.

Therefore, all universities which adopted IRIS have now an open access portal where they can deposit publications making them available in open access according to OA policies in effect within the same universities and in respect of rights of authorship.

Metadata relative to publications indexed in the IRIS archives are indexed also in the portal [PLEIADI \(Portale per la Letteratura scientifica Italiana Archivi e Depositi Istituzionali\)](#) / Portal for the Italian scientific literature archives and institutional stores) where it is possible to make a search filtering only the open access scientific publications which until 2015 are more than 100,000.

DATA MINING

DATA MINING is a mix of techniques and methodologies dealing with:

- The extraction of knowing or knowledge from big quantities of data (through automatic or semi-automatic methods)
- The scientific, industrial or operative use of this knowledge

DIGITAL SCIENCE

“DIGITAL SCIENCE is about the way research is carried out, disseminated, deployed and transformed by digital tools, networks and media.”

Internet technologies, large-scale computing and storage resources, data search/retrieval tools, mobile devices, social media, and their high uptake among different groups of people have profoundly changed the ways knowledge is created, communicated and how it can be further deployed.

They have made possible a radical transformation of the nature of science and innovation.

This Digital science relies on the use of e-infrastructures, i.e. ICT-based services and tools for data- and compute-intensive research in virtual and collaborative environments, combined with an internet culture for openness and collaboration.

The new tools and the new research cultures make it possible not only to perform research more efficiently but to create new types of science and research which is more open, more global and collaborative, more creative, and closer to society.

However, there are specific policy challenges relating to harnessing the full potential of Digital science. It would require changing traditional research systems and cultures to better appreciate and reward openness and collaboration.

In order to bring most benefits, it would require the widest possible take-up by European research organisations and different disciplines.

It would also require recognising and addressing possible risks and negative effects of these new ways of doing research.

Therefore, there is a need to support effective development and deployment of Digital science for achieving most benefits for science, society, policy and innovation in Europe.

DOAJ = Directory of Open Access Journals

URL <https://doaj.org/>

The Directory of Open Access Journals was launched in 2003 at Lund University, Sweden, with 300 open access journals and today contains ca. 9.000 open access journals covering all areas of science, technology, medicine, social science and humanities.

DOAJ is a membership organisation and membership is available in 3 main categories: [Publisher](#), [Ordinary Member](#) and [Sponsor](#). A DOAJ Membership is a clear statement of intent and proves a commitment to quality, peer-reviewed open access.

DOAJ is co-author to the [Principles of Transparency and Best Practice in Scholarly Publishing \(Principles\)](#) and DOAJ members are expected to follow these principles as a condition of membership.

DOAJ is a community-curated list of open access journals and aims to be the starting point for all information searches for quality, peer-reviewed open access material. To assist libraries and indexers keep their lists up-to-date, we make public a list of journals that have been [accepted into or removed from](#) DOAJ but we will not discuss specific details of an application with anyone apart from the applicant. Neither will we discuss individual publishers or applications with members of the public unless we believe that, doing so, we will be making a positive contribution to the open access community.

DOAJ publishes [Information for Publishers](#) on this site to help Publishers adhere to the Principles and to assist them in completing [an application](#). DOAJ also publishes [a list of FAQs](#) relevant to all members of the publishing community, particularly libraries and authors. All information on this site is available to both members and non-members.

The aim of the DOAJ is to increase the visibility and ease of use of open access scientific and scholarly journals, thereby promoting their increased usage and impact. The DOAJ aims to be comprehensive and cover all open access scientific and scholarly journals that use a quality control system to guarantee the content. In short, the DOAJ aims to be the one-stop shop for users of open access journals.

DOI = Digital Object Identifier

- DOI is a standard allowing within a digital net for the durable identification of every intellectual property object, and for its association to the relative reference data, or metadata, according to a structured and expandable method.
- DOI has been defined the “bar code for intellectual property”. Similarly to bar codes for physical products the use of DOI represents an added value and allow for the saving of resources along the productive and commercial chain.
- DOI is different from common internet indicators, such us URLs, because it identifies an object directly as a first class entity and not simply through some of its attributes such as the place where the object is located.
- DOI is different from common intellectual property indicators, such as indicators connected to bibliographic standards (ISBN, ISRC, ecc ...), because it is immediately operable online, and useable for the development of specific services, such as search engines, authenticity certifications, etc
- DOIs can be used to identify texts, images, audio or video resources, software, etc ... An object can be identified at any level of granularity: a DOI can be recorded onto a magazine masthead, one of its single numbers, one of its single articles, one single table of an article.
- DOI is an alphanumeric string divided in two parts: a *prefix* and a *suffix*, for example 10.1000/abc (or 10.1000/ABC). The suffix belonging to a prefix datum must be unique. DOIs are operable on internet which means they can be used to solve the content they identify, or resources correlated to the identified content. Unlike URLs, DOIs are associated to contents and not to places in the net. Thus, if a document location is changed users are redirected to reach the right page.
- In the example “10.1000/abc”, “10.1000” is the prefix, “10” identifies the string DOI, “1000” identifies the owner, “abc” is the suffix which identifies the digital object.

e-RESEARCH

e-Research has been defined in 2006.

e-Research encapsulates research activities that use a spectrum of advanced ICT capabilities and embraces new research methodologies emerging from increasing access to:

- broad band communications networks, research instruments and facilities, sensor networks, data repositories with their associated data standards and management tools and high performance computing resources;
- software and infrastructure services that enable a trust and sharing relationship to be established between researchers and the wide variety of data repositories, computers, systems and networks on which they depend;

and

- application and discipline-specific tools such as graphics intensive visualisation, simulation software, and interaction tools that provide the human interface allowing researchers to interact with each other and with their instruments, computational facilities and data resources."

e-SCIENCE

e-Science is the exploitation of ICT¹ research tools and infrastructures.

<p><i>In the future, e-Science will refer to the large scale science that will increasingly be carried out through distributed global collaborations enabled by the Internet.</i></p> <p><i>Typically, a feature of such collaborative scientific enterprises is that they will require access to very large data collections, very large scale computing resources and high performance visualisation back to the individual user scientists.</i></p>	<p>Processing large data</p>
	<p>Distributed researcher collaboration</p>

FAIR Open data

Dove FAIR sta per:

- F = Findable
- A = Accessible
- I = Interoperable
- R = Reusable

- **To be Findable:** assign persistent IDs, rich metadata, register repository in a searchable resource ...
- **To be Accessible:** retrievable by their ID using a standard protocol, metadata remain accessible even if data are no longer available ...
- **To be Interoperable:** use formal, broadly applicable languages, use standard vocabularies, qualified references ...
- **To be Reusable:** rich, accurate metadata, clear licenses, provenance, use of community standards ...

ISSN = International Standard Serial Number

¹ICT = Information and Communication Technologies.

What is an ISSN?

An ISSN is an 8-digit code used to identify newspapers, journals, magazines and periodicals of all kinds and on all media—print and electronic.

- Which publications are concerned by an ISSN?
- What form does an ISSN take?
- What is its role?
- Where is it displayed?

Which publications are concerned by an ISSN?

An ISSN (International Standard Serial Number) identifies all continuing resources, irrespective of their medium (print or electronic):

- newspapers,
- annual publications (reports, directories, lists, etc.),
- journals,
- magazines,
- collections,
- websites,
- databases,
- blogs, etc.

In many countries, an ISSN is mandatory for all publications subject to the legal deposit.

OACA = Open Access Citation Advantage

If you post your paper online somewhere outside a paywall, you join the majority of scholars and your paper will gain a citation advantage over papers available only through a journal.

This has been demonstrated in recent research (but other studies do not confirm it).

A particular focus of research on open access publishing has been the hypothesis that open access papers will be more highly cited.

OJS = Open Journal Systems

Open Journal Systems (<https://openjournalsystems.com/>) is a Phoenix-based technology² company that provides premium services and technical support for Open Journal Systems (OJS) and online journal publishing.

Founded in 2013, OpenJournalSystems.com has helped academic professionals, research institutions, and universities around the world establish online journals using the Open Journal Systems (OJS) software.

It offers variety of journal-hosting solutions, guidance, and advice to scientist, researchers, and editors to help create and share global knowledge and disseminate their digital content using its journal-hosting platform.

²Phoenix Technologies Ltd is an American company that designs, develops and supports core [system software](#) for [personal computers](#) and other computing devices. The company's products - commonly referred to as [BIOS](#) (Basic Input/Output System) or firmware - support and enable the compatibility, connectivity, security and management of the various components and technologies used in such devices.

OpenJournalSystems.com currently hosts more than 100 open access journals using Open Journal Systems.

Products and services include managed hosting and installations, theme, workflow and plugin customization, software upgrade, premium expert support, training, programming, editorial services and more.

OPEN ACCESS

Definizioni di "Open Access":

2002 - URL: <http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/>

2003 - URL: <http://legacy.earlham.edu/~peters/fos/bethesda.htm>

2003 - URL: <https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Declaration>

Open Access publishing is becoming an alternative and increasingly popular model for disseminating research papers. It offers three distinct models (and numerous variants of all three):

- GOLD - The publisher, which creates the final published form of the paper (i.e. usually a PDF) makes that final published form freely available.
The key point is that the publisher is responsible for making the work freely available.
- GREEN - The publisher locks the final published form of the paper behind a paywall, but the author takes steps to ensure that it's freely available elsewhere.
The key point is that the author has to make this happen, rather than leaving it to the publisher.
- LIBRE

In the Gold Open Access, in simple terms, the author publishes the paper in an OA journal or a book, supported by OA publisher. The terms of publication are the same as in the case of traditional publishers, except that the published paper is freely available to the public.

The Gold Open Access does not charge the reader and assigns the costs (APCs) to the author, although it should be noted that an increasing number of OA publishers waive these charges.

OPERAS = OPEn Research And Science group

URL <http://sp7.irea.cnr.it/operas/>

Team of ISMAR and IREA scientists interested in:

- Open Access
- Open Data
- Open Source Software
- Open Licences

- Open Hardware

ORCID = Open Researcher and Contributor ID

URL <https://orcid.org/>

ORCID is a nonprofit organization helping create a world in which all who participate in research, scholarship and innovation are uniquely identified and connected to their contributions and affiliations, across disciplines, borders, and time.

ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) is a non-proprietary [alphanumeric code](#) to uniquely identify [scientific](#) and other [academic authors](#) and contributors. This addresses the problem that a particular author's contributions to the [scientific literature](#) or publications in the [humanities](#) can be hard to recognize as most [personal names](#) are not unique, they can change (such as with marriage), have cultural differences in name order, contain inconsistent use of first-name abbreviations and employ different [writing systems](#). It provides a persistent identity for humans, similar to that created for content-related entities on digital networks by [digital object identifiers](#) (DOIs).

The ORCID organization offers an open and independent registry intended to be the *de facto* standard for contributor identification in research and [academic publishing](#).

REPOSITORY

A repository is the environment of an informative system (for example an ERP A repository is the environment of an informative system (for example an ERP³ type system) where metadata are managed through relational tables.

RIS = Research Information Systems

RIS is a standardized tag format developed by Research Information Systems, Incorporated (the format name refers to the company) to enable citation programs to exchange data. It is supported by a number of [reference managers](#). Many [digital libraries](#), like [IEEE Xplore](#), [Scopus](#), the [ACM Portal](#), [Scopemed](#), [ScienceDirect](#), [SpringerLink](#) and [Rayyan QCRI](#) can export citations in this format. Major reference/citation manager applications, like [Zotero](#), [Mendeley](#), and [EndNote](#) can export and import citations in this format.

SPARC = the Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition

URL: <https://sparcopen.org/>

³ERP, Enterprise Resource Planning (literally "planning of enterprise resources") is a management system (called informative system in informatics) which integrates all significant business processes within a company (sale, purchase, store management, accounting, etc ...). With the increase of the ERP popularity and the decrease of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) cost applications to help business managers to implement this methodology in their own business activities have been developed, such as: inventory control, orders' traceability, client services, finance and human resources.

- SPARC is a global coalition committed to making *Open* the default for research and education.
- SPARC empowers people to solve big problems and make new discoveries through the adoption of policies and practices that advance *Open Access*, *Open Data*, and *Open Education*.

SCIENCE

According to Merriam-Webster dictionary, Science is defined as:

- *knowledge or a system of knowledge covering general truths or the operation of general laws especially as obtained and tested through scientific method*
- *such knowledge or such a system of knowledge concerned with the physical world and its phenomena*

Science can be both considered as related to specific fields relating to studying the physical world (natural science) or as a general mode of solving problems and obtaining knowledge through the scientific method⁴.

SCIENCE 2.0

Science 2.0 is another term without a clear definition but with some usage in online discussions. It is less used than Open Science, but refers to the same openness during all the scientific process, emphasising the Web2.0 tools as the means for open collaboration, between all interested participants, whether scientists or amateurs.

Burgelman et al. (2010) defined Science 2.0 to be the change in science coming from the trends created by collaborative online tools and open scientific models:

- increased number of scientific authors (both professional and amateurs);
- increased number of scientific publications (different types of intermediate and discussion outputs in addition to traditional scientific papers);
- increased amount of data and its processing through the new availability of data from both official and unofficial sources.

⁴The scientific method consists of “principles and procedures for the systematic pursuit of knowledge involving the recognition and formulation of a problem, the collection of data through observation and experiment, and the formulation and testing of hypotheses”.

Science 2.0 trends in the research cycle

(From: Digital Science in Horizon2020; Annex I)

SCOPUS

Scopus is the largest abstract and citation database of peer-reviewed literature: scientific journals, books and conference proceedings.

Delivering a comprehensive overview of the world's research output in the fields of science, technology, medicine, social sciences, and arts and humanities, Scopus features smart tools to track, analyse and visualize research.

As research becomes increasingly global, interdisciplinary and collaborative, you can make sure that critical research from around the world is not missed when you choose Scopus.

SHERPA/RoMEO

It is a service run by [SHERPA](http://www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/index.php) (URL <http://www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/index.php>) to show the copyright and [open access self-archiving](#) policies of academic journals.

The database uses a colour-coding scheme to classify publishers according to their self-archiving policy.

This shows authors whether the journal allows [preprint](#) or [post-print](#) archiving in their copyright transfer agreements.

It currently holds records for over 22,000 journals.

	GOLD	open access publishing
	GREEN	can archive pre-print and post-print
	BLUE	can archive post-print (ie final draft post-refereeing)
	YELLOW	can archive pre-print (ie pre-refereeing)
	WHITE	archiving not formally supported

TCP = Total Cost of Publication

The TCP, or “Total Cost of Publication”, comprises subscription costs plus APCs and additional administration costs.